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Kasimova Adiba NasirovnaSenior lecturer of the
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages**TRANSLATION METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF PUBLICISTIC MATERIALS** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642168>**ABSTRACT**

This article deals with the analysis of the translation activity based on the publicistic texts. By means of real situational examples taken from mass media materials students will learn the methods of translation, master the techniques of carrying out the adequate translation in compliance with the source resulting in implementing acquired knowledge and skill in practice. Along with studying the translation methods students will obtain the skills of using appropriate transformational technique in rendering translation examples from ST (Source Text) into TT (Target Text).

Key words: information, English, genre, ching, context, situation, translation, method, style, practice, transformation, competence, professionalism, skill, ST (Source Text), TT (Target Text).

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Самаркандский государственный институт иностранных языков**МЕТОДЫ И ПРИЕМЫ ПЕРЕВОДА ПУБЛИЦИСТИЧЕСКИХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье рассматривается анализ переводческой деятельности на основе публицистических текстов. На реальных ситуационных примерах, взятых из материалов СМИ, студенты будут изучать приемы перевода, осваивать приемы выполнения адекватного перевода в соответствии с источником, в результате чего полученные знания и навыки будут реализованы на практике.

Наряду с изучением методов перевода студенты получают навыки использования соответствующей техники трансформации при воспроизведении примеров осуществляя перевод с ИТ (Исходный текст) на ПТ (Переводной текст).

Ключевые слова: информация, английский язык, жанр, обучение, контекст, ситуация, перевод, метод, стиль, практика, трансформация, компетентность, профессионализм, умение, ИТ (Исходный текст), ПТ (Переводной текст).

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Samarqand davlat chet tillar institute

PUBLITSISTIK MATERIALLARNI TARJIMA QILISH USULLARI VA TEXNIKASI

ANNOTATSUYA

Ushbu maqola publitsistik matnlar va misollar asosida tarjima jarayonida muhim texnikalarni o'rganish da talabalarga ushbu malakasini rivojlantirish jarayoniga ko'maklashishga bag'ishlangan. Haqiqiy vaziyatli misollar orqali talabalar tarjima usullarini o'rganadilar, berilgan manbalar yordamida adekvat tarjima qilish texnikasini o'zlashtiradilar, Natijada olingan bilim va ko'nikmalarni amalda qo'llashadi. Tarjima usullarini o'rganish bilan bir qatorda talabalar AT (Asliyat tilidagi matn)dan TT (Tarjima tilidagi matn)ga tarjima misollarini keltirishda tegishli transformatsiya usulidan foydalanish ko'nikmalariga ega bo'ladilar.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'lumot, ingliz tili, janr, o'qitish, kontekst, vaziyat, tarjima, uslub, amaliyot, transformatsiya, kompetensiya, professionallik, mahorat, AT (Asliyat tilidagi matn), TT (Tarjima tilidagi matn).

Nowadays the mass information medium has a huge influence on the public. It puts forward the most important information, and also contributes to the formation of one or another opinion about the information presented. Thus, it encourages the reader or listener to form their own attitude about the situation. In order to introduce media styles in the field of education, to broaden the horizons of foreign language learners, it is crucial to develop a teaching methodology. Consequently, it will be of great importance for English language learners to develop not only understanding, but also provide them with practical exercises to improve their translation competence in the field of translation theory and practice. Several styles of publicistic genre, about which it is already widely known, have their own tasks, functional styles, classifications, and their norms. If we talk about the publicistic genre, it should be noted here their classifications, in which they reflect their functional styles. Without a definite picture of the publicistic genre, it would be difficult to talk about a specific type of media represented.

We are presented with several types of classifications for analysis in the process of our work and in the future, it can become the main materials for students in mastering the methodology for developing translation techniques. Considering their types, we will have to clarify their definitions, and where possible provide examples for concretization: such as news materials, comments, analytical reviews, interviews, advertisements from newspapers, etc. in its turn, there are accepted terms and phrases in the field of mass media. As we already know, the texts submitted by journalists are called media linguists, and their written texts are called media texts. Before the texts are handed over to the hands of media linguists, they go through several instances, after the structure of the text having being carefully analyzed the information is considered to convey public. By the decree of President Sh. M. Mirziyayev, an urgent problem in the field of journalism in the coverage of information by our journalists was presented and discussed, to improve their ability to know several languages. This issue is undoubtedly important and, having knowledge of a foreign language, will present young specialists to develop professionalism and introduce their theoretical knowledge into practice. Here the informant, that is, the media linguist, will prove himself not only as a specialist who presents the task of conveying information, but also as an expert of his work. Sometimes, referring to his abilities, a media linguist performs the work of a translator, switching from SL into TL.

To present a high-quality translation of a publicistic style, the translator should have knowledge of the theory and practice of translation. It should be noted that when engaged in translation activities, a specialist needs to know the terminology of the field with which he is dealing with. Today, the translators are presented with the task of mastering several foreign languages. And this is their advantage in the transferring of information, which shows their professionalism. Thus, the following methods of translating newspaper journalistic articles are presented. These important methods are typical in the translation of articles from the SL into TL. There are a huge number of classifications of translation transformations. As V.N. Kamissarov believes that transformation is one of the most important methods of translation, distinguishing it as grammatical and lexical

transformations. Apparently, translators should skillfully implement the related lexical and semantic substitutions when they deal with English texts. Thus, students specialized in translation master translation skills, study the functional style of the text, its ideology, subject matter and vocabulary, etc. As mentioned earlier, the media is one of the interesting subjects' matter for foreign language learners. For better and effective acquisition of the English language, the exercises based on publicistic genre are presented, so that translators can interpret texts considering the training activities and the methodology for assimilating media materials. So, we collect texts aimed at teaching not only information materials with ad hoc terminology, but also with the help of this students will develop their translation skill [1, p. 55-59].

It is also important to note that while carrying out translation process translators should pay attention to the difference in the grammatical structure and word use of foreign languages, the difference in the mentality of people who use these languages as native languages, which are reflected in the discrepancy between linguistic and cultural realities. Hence, it is possible to consider several necessary practical skills to overcome translation difficulties in real life situations [2, p. 11].

1. Knowledge of the area of the translation text

A specialist translator needs to have or acquire certain knowledge in the field to which the translation text belongs, to study special terminology. We often meet with inadequate translation of the material, the reason for this is the wrong choice of words and expressions. In order to get a literate and adequate translation, the translator is recommended to take an interest in and get acquainted with the materials and publications in this area.

The meaning of words in English and Russian, Uzbek (not always) languages correspond to each other. The meaning of an English word is conveyed by the same equivalent. These words include nouns, numerals, days of the week and months, scientific and technical terms, place names, etc. There is also a variant match, when the meaning of an English word corresponds to several words in the native language. In this situation, the translator needs to consider the context in which a certain word is used. There are a lot of examples [4, p. 19], you can see where the variant coincidence occurs.

The word Variability has a slightly different translation, corresponding in Russian: вариативность, изменчивость, неровность, неустойчивость.

Variability of temper –изменчивость настроения

Data variability –вариативность данных

Variability of character –неровность характера

Variability of prices -неустойчивость цен

As you can see in examples 1 and 3, it is replaced by the same word, since it is contextually more consistent with the given word. When, like in Russian, a different word was used in each context.

To make a more accurate translation, you need to use special dictionaries, the certain dictionaries make it possible to carry out a competent translation.

2. International words and "false friends" of the translator

International or borrowed words converge in sound, spelling and meaning.

English	Russian	Uzbek
Contrast	контраст	kontrast
Dumping	демпинг	demping
Manager	менеджер	menejer
Inflation	инфляция	inflyatsiya
Philosophy	философия	falsafa
Television	телевидение	televideniye

The latter used method of teaching the translation of texts in the specialty, using the component of the origin of special terms, i.e. their etymology is the problem-activity approach, which considers that during the training sessions the student does not receive information "on a platter", but acquires knowledge himself, while the teacher plays the role of a mentor and assistant.

While teaching the ways of translation in practice we come across with some word combinations only used in mass media, not knowing the adequate interpretation of the meaning the

sense of the text can be lost. Having been acknowledged with the exact contextual meaning the effect of the text will have accurate interpretation. Some may conclude the meaning by making word for word translation, however, it does not work right and disclose the concept in TT. One may find out the definitions of the word combinations in their TT so easily that hindrance may raise in concluding with their existed equivalents. The subject matter of the task is to approach the contextual meaning at most. Let us to settle down to the study of the word combination in practice.

3. Translation of word combinations related to Mass media [5, p. 40-41].

Word combinations in ST	Definitions in ST	Translation in TT/ Russian	Translation in TT/Uzbek	Example
Cold calling	The practice of telephoning somebody you do not know, in order to sell them something [6]	холодное прозванивание [посещение]	sotuvchi oldindan kelishilmagan holda mijozga qo'ng'iroq qilish yoki tashrif buyurish amaliyoti	Things are a little slow here, and there's only so much cold calling you can do in a day.
Mass marketing	Producing for very large numbers of people [6]	массовый маркетинг	Ommaviy marketing	Mass marketing and advertising will encourage us to conform to some culturally-constructed ideal, rather than celebrate, or even accept, differences .
Subliminal messages	messages that we are not consciously aware of and we can't become aware of	Подсознательное послание	Ongli ravishda xabardor bo'lmagan xabarlar	Section 5 imposes on broadcasters the duty to ensure that broadcast programmes do not contain subliminal messages .
Negative publicity	unpleasant, depressing, or harmful information or actions that are intended to attract the public's attention	Негативная информация, негативный резонанс	Zararli yoki salbiy oshkoralik (ma'lumot)	That has also been worsened by the negative publicity by the mainstream western media about the country.

Generic advertising	a type of marketing designed to promote a general product rather than a specific brand name	Типовая реклама	Umumiy reklama	The Irish Tourism Board has begun a \$20-million generic advertising campaign on behalf of the hospitality industry.
Prime time	the time at which a radio or television audience is expected to be at its highest [6]	Лучшее эфирное время	Eng ko'p auditoriyaga ega bo'lgan efir vaqti	Prime time advertising slots are always more expensive on account of the number of people tuning in.
Brand recognition	the ability of consumers to identify a specific brand by its attributes over another one	Узнаваемость бренда, осведомленность о марке	Tovar haqida xabardor bo'lish	MacDonald's scores very highly in the brand recognition stakes; it is one of the best-known in existence.
The classifieds	The section in a newspaper with small advertisements arranged in groups according to their subject, that are placed by people or small companies who want to buy or sell something, find or offer a job [6]	Объявление о работе	E'lonlar	I found a job that might be of interest to you in the classifieds under "Teaching Posts".
The watershed	the time after which programmes that are regarded as unsuitable for children are broadcast on television	Вечерний час эфира ТВ	Kechki soat efir dasturlari	They allow graphic imagery like that to be shown after the watershed.
Billboard/hoarding	a large outdoor board for displaying advertisements [6]	доска для объявлений, афиш, СМИ рекламная вставка	E'lonlar taxtasi	Out on the freeway, a billboard caught his eye.
Jingle	a short slogan, verse, or tune designed to be easily remembered, especially as used in advertising [6]	джингл, музыкальный рекламный ролик	Reclama qo'shig'i/roligi	The Coca-Cola jingle

Slogan/catchphrase	a well-known sentence or phrase, especially one that is associated with a particular famous person [6]	популярное выражение	Diqqatni tortadigan soʻz yoki mashhur ibora	That's your catchphrase , isn't it?
Focus group	a group of people assembled to participate in a discussion about a product before it is launched, or to provide feedback on a political campaign, television series, etc.	фокус-группа	teledasturlar va boshqalar haqida fikr-mulohazalar bildirish maqsadida yigʻilgan bir guruh	The focus group gave us surprising feedback which may prompt us to rethink our market-entry strategy and product positioning.

We deduce that analytical thinking of a translator who has basic knowledge in the professional field have got to be able to determine the communicative and pragmatic tasks of a foreign language source text. For a student, it is necessary to be able to correctly and reliably decompose the translation fragment into its constituent elements; learning to generalize and analyze the information received; being able to identify translation fragments and special terms that relate to different areas of science and differentiate in style. The student should also learn to reason the conclusions based on the results of the translation and generalize the information after the analysis.

References:

1. Nikolaeva O.S. Technique of teaching the translation of scientific texts based on considering the etymological signs of words: the main approaches and ways of implementation. Bulletin of the Tambov University named after G.R. Derzhavin. No. 8., p. 55-59.2010.
2. V.S.Slepovich “Translation”, p.11 Minsk. Tetra Systems 2009.
3. V.S.Slepovich Translation course, p.12-14. Tetra Systems 2001.
4. V.S.Slepovich Translation course, p. 19. Tetra Systems 2002.
5. Andrew Betsis, Sean Haughton “The Vocabulary files”, p. 40-41
6. Sally Wehmeier, Colin Mcintosh, Joanna Turnbull, Michael Ashby, Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, 7th edition, Oxford University Press 2008.

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

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